

BIOTRANSFORMING EU WINE AND DISTILLERY BY-PRODUCTS: GRAPE MARC VALORIZATION VIA EDIBLE FILAMENTOUS FUNGI FOR SUSTAINABLE PROTEIN PRODUCTION

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ABSTRACT: The growing demand for sustainable food systems and resource efficiency has intensified interest in the valorization of agri-food by-products. Grape marc, a major residue from the European wine and distillation industries, poses environmental challenges but offers significant potential for upcycling. This study presents a fungal-based biorefinery approach to convert grape marc into a protein-rich ingredient using edible filamentous fungi: *Aspergillus oryzae*, *Rhizopus delemar*, and *Neurospora intermedia*. Grape marc was hydrothermally pre-treated at 121 °C for 20 minutes to generate liquid cultivation media. Submerged fermentations were conducted under different GM liquor concentrations (2-8 %, w/v), pH (3.88, 5.0 and 6.0), and cultivation time (48 and 72 hours). In addition, supplementation with 1 mL/L vitamins and 10 mL/L trace metal solution was tested. Optimal fungal biomass yield and crude protein content was achieved by using 4% GM liquor, at pH 5.0, over 72 hours, with *Neurospora intermedia* outperforming other strains in both fungal biomass yield and crude protein content. This study highlights the potential of grape marc biotransformation through fungal fermentation, offering benefits such as upcycling into high-value products, improving resource efficiency, supporting sustainable food systems, and opening new avenues for research in biorefineries.

Keywords: biorefinery, biobased products, circular economy, fermentation, proteins.

1 INTRODUCTION

For meeting global food and nutritional requirements, in the perspectives of an increasing population toward 2050, sustainable food systems are vital. Effective recovery and upcycling of agrifood industries side streams and by-products are essential to enhance the sustainability and to contribute to the European Union (EU) circular economy principles. The wine and distillery industries represent the largest agri-food sector in the European Union, playing a significant role in both the economy and agricultural production. However, they face pressing challenges related to waste generation, with approximately 20 million tons of waste generated annually worldwide, of which the EU accounts for 14.5 million tons. The most significant by-product is grape marc (GM). Typically GM represents 20-30% of the processed grape weight, constitutes up to 60% of solid waste, and by contributing worldwide around 10-13.5 million tons per year [1].

Although GM poses environmental management challenges due to its high organic load, acidity, and polyphenolic content, it also holds substantial potential for valorization into value-added products within the framework of a circular bioeconomy [1]. In the past decade, GM valorization has attracted increasing interest from both the scientific community and industry. Recent studies suggest incorporating GM into an integrated biorefinery model, to bioconvert GM into value-added products or to recover high-value compounds by utilizing filamentous fungi (e.g., *Actinomucor elegans*, *A. awamori*, *A. oryzae*, *A. niger*, *A. brasiliensis*, *P. chrysosporium*, *R. oryzae*, *T. asperellum*, *T. reesei*, *T. virde*, *N. sitophila* and *U. isabelline*). The fungal fermentation of GM has shown to increase protein, ash and free fat content of the biomass [1,2]. Via solid state or submerged fermentation, fungi have been explored for enzyme production [2,3], bioproduction of citric acid [4], and sugars extraction [5]. In addition, fungal fermentation has been explored for the recovery of bioactive compounds, to obtain extracts with enhanced antioxidant and prebiotic activities [6], and for recovery of polyphenols [2], gallic acid, ellagic acid, condensed tannins, flavonoids, sterols, fatty acids, γ -linolenic acid and carotenoids [7].

Despite efforts on GM valorization through fungal fermentation, few studies looked at *A. oryzae* and *R. delemar*, and there are no studies exploring *N. intermedia* fermentation of GM. This study aims to develop and implement innovative approaches to valorize organic by-products from EU distilleries and wine industries by including grape marc (GM) into a fungal-based biorefinery model. By integrating edible filamentous fungi (*Aspergillus oryzae*, *Rhizopus delemar*, and *Neurospora intermedia*) to biotransform GM into protein-rich biomass, this study evaluates submerged fermentation under varied conditions, identifying the best cultivation conditions that maximize both biomass yield and protein content, with scale-up perspectives.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Substrate

Grape marc (GM) was kindly provided by Acquavite Distillery (Vazzola, Italy) in November 2023. GM solutions were prepared at concentrations of 2%, 4%, 6%, and 8% (w/v) to serve as cultivation media. The GM liquors were produced via hydrothermal pretreatment at 121 °C for 20 minutes, followed by centrifugation and filtration.

2.2 Fungi strains

Three edible filamentous fungal strains, obtained from Westerdijk Fungal Biodiversity Institute, The Netherlands, (*Rhizopus oryzae* var. *delemar* CBS 145940, *Aspergillus oryzae* var. *oryzae* CBS 819.72, and *Neurospora intermedia* CBS 131.92) were used for cultivations. The fungal strains were maintained on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA), containing 4 g/L potato extract (SigmaAldrich, Buchs, Switzerland), 20 g/L glucose (Fisher Scientific, Loughborough, UK) and 15 g/L agar (Sigma, Buchs, Switzerland).

2.3 Fungal cultivation

Cultivations were carried out in 250 mL baffled Erlenmeyer flasks, each inoculated with 2 mL of spore suspension per 100 mL of GM liquor (Table I).

Table I: Overview of fungal cultivations

Configuration	Shake flasks	Shake flasks
Working volume	100 mL	100 mL
Substrate concentration (% w/v)	2, 6, 8	4
Temperature (°C)	35	35
Agitation (rpm)	115	115
Supplements	NS, S	NS, S
pH	5	3.88, 5, 6
Cultivation time (hours)	72	48, 72
Fungus strain	<i>A.oryze</i> , <i>N.intermedia</i> , <i>R.deleamar</i>	<i>A.oryze</i> , <i>N.intermedia</i> , <i>R.deleamar</i>

The flasks were incubated in a water bath at 35°C with shaking at 115 rpm for up to 72 hours. Three pH conditions were tested: the initial uncontrolled pH of 3.88, and controlled pH values of 5.0 and 6.0, which were maintained during fermentation by adding either 2 M H₂SO₄ or 2 M NaOH (Sigma-Aldrich, Darmstadt, Germany). Cultivations were performed with and without supplementation; the supplemented medium (S) received 1 mL/L vitamin solution and 10 mL/L trace metal solution, while non-supplemented (NS) media received none.

Biomass was harvested using a kitchen sieve (1 mm² pore size), rinsed with distilled water, and dried overnight at 70°C. Biomass yield was determined gravimetrically, and crude protein content was calculated from the nitrogen content, using a factor of 6.25 [8]. All experiments were conducted in duplicate.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Fungal cultivation on grape marc and metabolites dynamics

This study investigates a biovalorization route for grape marc (GM), an organic by-product from EU distilleries and wineries, by integrating into a fungal-based biorefinery model. A key strategy involves using GM as a substrate for fungal cultivation to produce protein-rich ingredients for food and feed applications. The composition of GM supports its potential for conversion into value-added products within a circular bioeconomy framework [1].

Grape marc (GM) was bioconverted using edible filamentous fungi (*Aspergillus oryzae*, *Rhizopus deleamar*, *Neurospora intermedia*) in submerged fermentation with 2–8% (w/v) hydrothermally pretreated GM liquors. Fungal growth was tracked over 72 hours at pH 5.0 under both supplemented and non-supplemented conditions, providing insight into the feasibility of utilizing this complex lignocellulosic substrate for protein-rich fungal biomass production. In addition, the metabolite dynamics of *Aspergillus oryzae*, *Neurospora intermedia*, and *Rhizopus deleamar* were evaluated to assess their utilization of key carbon sources during cultivation in liquid grape marc (GM) media, as presented in Fig. 1 to 3.

As shown in Fig. 1, *Aspergillus oryzae* efficiently utilized sugars, reducing concentrations near to zero within 48–60 hours, indicating active fermentation. Ethanol (EtOH) levels peaked between 12 and 24 hours, then declined after 24–36 hours, likely due to re-

assimilation as a carbon source or loss via evaporation. Supplementation with vitamins and trace metals slightly accelerated substrate utilization, suggesting enhanced metabolic activity.

Glycerol concentrations gradually decreased, while acetic acid declined slowly, potentially consumed by the cells. Overall, *A. oryzae* demonstrated efficient fermentation with moderate ethanol production and rapid sugar utilization. Similar metabolic trends were observed between non-supplemented and supplemented conditions, although supplementation enhanced glucose uptake and accelerated ethanol turnover, supporting faster metabolism.

Figure 1: Metabolite dynamics of *Aspergillus oryzae* cultivated in 2–8% (w/v) grape marc (GM) liquor at pH 5.0 over 72 hours, under non-supplemented (NS) and supplemented (S: vitamin and trace metal solution) conditions. Measured metabolites include glucose (Glu), acetic acid (Ace), glycerol (Gly), ethanol (EtOH), and a mixture of sugars (Sug Mix).

As illustrated in Fig. 2, *Neurospora intermedia* exhibited a strong and steady decline in glucose and mixed sugars. Ethanol (EtOH) levels remained higher and sustained for a longer duration compared to *A. oryzae*.

Figure 2: Metabolite dynamics of *Neurospora intermedia* cultivated in 2–8% (w/v) grape marc (GM) liquor at pH 5.0 over 72 hours, under non-supplemented (NS) and supplemented (S: vitamin and trace metal solution) conditions. Measured metabolites include glucose (Glu), acetic acid (Ace), glycerol (Gly), ethanol (EtOH), and a mixture of sugars (Sug Mix).

Glycerol and acetic acid concentrations also showed a gradual, stable decrease. These findings suggest that *N. intermedia* maintains ethanol presence longer, possibly due to reduced re-assimilation or loss via evaporation, or slower downstream metabolism, while efficiently utilizing sugars.

Similar trends were observed under supplemented conditions; however, ethanol began declining earlier, indicating more rapid consumption or conversion, and glucose was depleted slightly sooner. Overall, supplementation enhances sugar uptake and metabolic turnover, though *N. intermedia* performs effectively under both supplemented and non-supplemented conditions.

Figure 3: Metabolite dynamics of *Rhizopus delemar* cultivated in 2–8% (w/v) grape marc (GM) liquor at pH 5.0 over 72 hours, under non-supplemented (NS) and supplemented (S: vitamin and trace metal solution) conditions. Measured metabolites include glucose (Glu), acetic acid (Ace), glycerol (Gly), ethanol (EtOH), and a mixture of sugars (Sug Mix).

Metabolite dynamics of *Rhizopus delemar* cultivated in 2–8% GM liquor (Fig. 3) indicate that this strain produces the highest ethanol levels during the early stages of fermentation. It also exhibits rapid sugar uptake and appears to perform effectively under non-supplemented conditions.

4 DISCUSSION

All fungal strains exhibited rapid consumption of glucose and mixed sugars within the first 48 hours. Efficient glucose utilization occurred primarily within the first 24 hours, with *A. oryzae* and *N. intermedia* utilizing most of the available glucose, indicating short lag phases and active glycolytic metabolism. These observations align with previous studies that identify glucose as the preferred carbon source for most fungi due to its direct entry into glycolysis [10]. *R. delemar* also consumed glucose effectively but showed a slight delay, likely reflecting differences in initial growth dynamics or regulation of glucose uptake.

Among the fungi tested, only *Aspergillus oryzae* demonstrated significant glycerol utilization (~89%), likely due to its robust glycerol kinase and glycerol dehydrogenase activities. In contrast, *Neurospora intermedia* and *Rhizopus delemar* showed minimal glycerol uptake, possibly due to repression under glucose-rich conditions or inherently lower glycerol transport and

metabolism capacities. This finding is particularly relevant when using substrates that contain residual glycerol from fermentation. *Rhizopus delemar* efficiently utilized acetic acid (~80%) over 72 hours, indicating its ability to thrive in low-pH environments with moderate acetic acid concentrations. *A. oryzae* showed lower acetic acid utilization (~55%). Despite the known toxicity of acetic acid, *N. intermedia* also utilized it extensively, suggesting adaptation to acetic acid-containing substrates. Glycerol, a typical osmoprotectant and redox-balancing metabolite, decreased over time, implying its involvement in secondary metabolism. Moderate acetic acid levels throughout cultivation suggest the absence of strong acid stress.

All tested fungi produced ethanol, with *Rhizopus delemar* demonstrating the highest efficiency, particularly under non-supplemented conditions, indicating strong ethanologenic potential. *R. delemar* maintained elevated ethanol levels by 24 hours, reflecting robust fermentative capacity under limited oxygen availability. This aligns with known metabolic pathways in *Mucorales* fungi, which shift to ethanol production under oxygen-limited or sugar-rich environments. However, ethanol concentrations declined after peaking, suggesting *R. delemar* can metabolize ethanol post-fermentation, showcasing metabolic flexibility between fermentation and oxidative pathways. In contrast, *Aspergillus oryzae* and *Neurospora intermedia* produced relatively low ethanol levels, indicating a preference for aerobic metabolism and biomass synthesis over ethanol excretion. While *A. oryzae* exhibits moderate ethanol tolerance, *N. intermedia* is more sensitive and may experience inhibition at ethanol concentrations above 2–3% [10].

In the utilization of mixed sugars, *Aspergillus oryzae* demonstrated the most robust consumption, consistent with its high production of extracellular hydrolases such as xylanases and pectinases, which are essential for degrading complex polysaccharides. *Neurospora intermedia* and *Rhizopus delemar* also adapted well to the complex grape marc cultivation media.

Supplementation with vitamins and trace metals supported metabolic efficiency but did not significantly alter metabolite profiles, suggesting it fine-tunes rather than fundamentally reshapes fungal metabolism.

The fungal growth was influenced by GM concentration, indicating that factors beyond carbon availability—such as the presence of inhibitory compounds, fiber-rich matrix effects, and potential nutrient imbalances—may influence fungal performance. These findings align with prior reports highlighting the multifaceted challenges associated with cultivating microorganisms on agro-industrial by-products.

In addition, substrate accessibility and fermentation conditions, particularly pH and nutrient supplementation, were observed to play a critical role in fungal growth dynamics. While a pH of 5.0 appeared to support better fungal performance across the tested strains, deviations from this value resulted in reduced biomass yields, potentially due to strain-specific pH sensitivities or alterations in substrate solubility and nutrient availability. Such outcomes emphasize the need for tailored pH control strategies in future process development.

Nutrient supplementation, involving the addition of trace elements and vitamins, had only a slight positive effect on fungi growth. This suggests that GM, even in its minimally processed form, may inherently contain certain micronutrients supportive of fungal metabolism.

Nevertheless, additional refinement or conditioning of GM—for instance, via mild chemical or enzymatic pretreatment—could further enhance substrate digestibility and nutrient release.

Additionally, the crude protein content in the fungal biomass was found to increase over time, suggesting ongoing nitrogen assimilation and potential species-specific protein biosynthesis pathways. While differences in protein accumulation were observed among the tested strains, further research is needed to understand the underlying metabolic traits and how they interact with environmental and nutritional factors during fermentation.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Submerged fermentation using edible filamentous fungi (*Aspergillus oryzae*, *Rhizopus delemar*, and *Neurospora intermedia*) successfully converted grape marc (GM) into protein-rich biomass, demonstrating its potential as a valuable substrate. Fungal biomass production varied among strains depending on GM concentration, pH, cultivation time, and supplementation. Across fungi species, *N. intermedia* exhibited the highest protein levels. The study identified optimal conditions for maximizing both biomass yield and crude protein content as 4% GM concentration, pH 5.0, and 72 hours of cultivation. These findings confirm GM's suitability for fungal cultivation, offering a viable route to produce protein-rich biomass.

This valorization strategy provides an alternative protein source, filamentous fungi-based, contributing to the sustainable utilization of enological by-products. Aligned with circular bioeconomy principles, it supports food security, enhances resource efficiency, and advances environmental sustainability goals. In addition, it advances current biotechnological practices by enabling the upcycling of GM into high-value products, and enhancing sustainable food systems. The study's outcomes support potential industrial applications in food, feed, and biotech sectors, reinforcing its broader significance.

While the present study results are promising, scaling up the process using bubble column reactors should be prioritized to facilitate industrial application. Additionally, future studies should explore the interplay between substrate characteristics and fungal physiology to better define the operational boundaries for the fungal valorization of grape marc and similar agro-industrial residues.

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